

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF SOLAR-POWERED SMART GARDEN CLEANER

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Abstract - The leaves that are found in the pathways, gardens, roads etc. are not disposed of properly and they cause pollution in the land. During autumn season the leaves are found to be larger in number, thus the people are spending more time and energy collecting the leaves. There is a need for a specific device which will be used to overcome this problem. In recent years a greater number of devices have been introduced for the purpose of collecting leaves and debris from the ground. In this, people are facing different issues such as size of the disposable bag, noise produced by the device, safety precaution when it is operated by current etc. To avoid this problem, we are developing a solar operated smart garden cleaning machine for the purpose of collecting the leaves and debris from the ground. The vacuum blower and the storage tank which is used for collecting the leaves are mounted on the main frame. The hole is created for connecting the vacuum blower and the storage tank. The electric motor is mounted on the corner of the main frame, and it is attached with the blade. When the power is generated from the solar which is stored in the batteries that should give to the vacuum blower collects the leaves due to the pressure difference created inside the vacuum blower. The collected leaves can be fed into the blade. The leaves are chopped well by the blade, and it is disposed.

Keywords: Smart garden cleaning, sensors, solar power, dry leaves collector machine.

1. Introduction:

Agricultural production gives considerable amount of agriculture waste. Some of it is recycled into agriculture as fertilizer while large amounts remain unused and, in many instances, pose a disposal problem. Uncontrolled burning in the fuel is not only the hazardous disposal solution, it also wastes useful energy with efficient collection system waste from agricultural production can be utilized as fuel for power and heat production. In some agriculture industries a large amount of biomass waste is already concentrated. The use of solar energy in grain drying can greatly reduce the use of fossil fuels, consequently reducing pollutant emission. However, there is no simple design tool for sizing solar-assisted crop dryers based on drying load, climate and economic data. This lack affects rural producers, who prefer to continue using traditional sources of energy. It also affects the small producer, who is deprived of technologies appropriate to the economic realities of rural areas in developing countries.

Leaves scattered on the parks, Gardens, and other places have a detrimental effect on the beauty of the environment, and decrease photosynthesis, hence, the efficiency of plants. Leaves are also used in the production of peat. This makes using leaves collectors in the garden, and organizations with a green space useful. Because leaves take up a high volume, their transportation is difficult. Using the machine, which was equipped with a suction-blower system, increases efficiency, and at the same time decreases the costs of green space, and their workforce cost. Focusing on overcoming the mentioned difficulties, this study was carried out to design and produce a Solar powered with suction-blower system.

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2. Literature Review :

Satyam Gupta, Abhishek Dohare, Vaibhav Shivhare[1] the purpose of this project is to design and create a floor and road cleaning machine for colleges, hospitals, auditoriums, and workshops. A “low-cost high-power sweeper with lattice blades” was created and developed as a new way of implementing street cleaning on streets and university floors. This paper presents the design and development of a mechanically operated leaf sweeping machine.

Brijesh K J, Karthik P, Adarsh S B, Githin V, Kevin Xavier[2] This project mainly concentrates on offering an easy, safety, reliable solution to the common problem of inefficient garbage disposal. If we can develop a suitable method to collect and store the waste in a trolley like waste collecting machine, we can reduce the effort by the labours during operation of work. If the system consists of both collection and storage in a single unit, the waste collection from difficult areas can be done easily with less amount of time.

Mayur Shelke, Sumit Badode, Vishesh Wasnik, Yash Badole, Tushar Patil, Ritesh Shende[3] This project is to make a clean environment with less human effort. The leaves that are collected are chopped well by the blade attached to the motor. The chopped leaves can be used as manure or mulch for gardening purposes. This project is collecting the leaves in the garden, roadways, pathways etc.

[Murugan P C, Vel Kumara Samy V, Vijaya Prasath S, Vishnu Bharathi T[4] The main aim of the leaf collector project is to make a clean environment with less human effort. The leaves that are collected are chopped well by the blade attached to the motor. The chopped leaves can be used as manure or mulch for gardening purposes. This project is collecting the leaves in the garden, roadways, pathways etc. Human power is reduced, and time consumption is reduced for collecting leaves.

Alireza SHIRNESHAN [5] have designed a vacuum section of a leaf collector machine in this paper design of vacuum section of the machine that is one of the main sections in the machine, is explained according to working condition and principal relations of fluid mechanic and vacuum fans and doing the experiment to determine air flow for vacuum leaves.

3.Experimental Work:

3.1 Components Used

□ Battery:

Figure. 3.1 Battery

Figure 3.1 shows 12V Battery is a type of rechargeable battery that provides a voltage output of 12 volts. These batteries are commonly used in various applications, including automotive vehicles, marine vessels, recreational vehicles, and off-grid solar systems.

Sealed Rechargeable battery.

AB 12V 7.2/12V-7.2 AH Voltage

Parameters

Constant Voltage Charge (27°C)

Cycle use: 14.1 V- 14.4 V

Max. Current; 1.4 A

- **Speed Regulator:**

Figure. 3.2 Knob type PWM speed regulator

Figure. 3.2 shows the Speed controller, also known as a motor controller or variable speed drive, is a device used to regulate the speed of an electric motor.

Input voltage: 12–60 V.

Maximum current: 50 A

Continuous current: 40 A

Speed regulation type: Current regulation.

- **Four-Channel relay Module:**

Figure. 3.3 shows A 4-channel relay is an electronic switch that controls multiple electrical circuits using a single control signal. Each relay within the module typically consists of a coil and multiple switch contacts.

Figure 3.3 Four-Channel Relay Module

Supply voltage – 3.75V to 6V.

Trigger current – 5mA.

Current when the relay is active - ~70mA (single), ~300mA (all four) Relay

maximum contact voltage – 250VAC, 30VDC.

Relay maximum current – 10A.

- **Suction Fan:**

Figure:3.4 Suction Fan 1000 CFM

Figure. 3.4 shows, A 1000 CFM (cubic feet per minute) suction fan is a type of ventilation fan designed to move air at a rate of 1000 cubic feet per minute. These fans are commonly used in various industrial, commercial, and residential applications where efficient air movement and ventilation are required.

Rated Voltage – 115V Rated

Current – 1.14/1.60A Input

Power – 129/180W.

Speed – 2500 / 2800 RPM.

Air Flow – 1000/1170

CFM.

- **Motors used:**

Figure: 3.5 Worm Geared DC Motor

Figure 3.5 shows A 12V DC motor integrated with a worm gear system is an excellent choice for applications demanding robust torque and precise control. The direct current motor operates efficiently at 12 volts, providing a reliable power source for various tasks. The incorporation of a worm gear mechanism enhances the motor's capabilities by significantly increasing torque output while reducing rotational speed.

Voltage – 12VDC

Speed – 100-200RPM.

Torque – 1-2Kgf.cm

- **Solar panel:**

Figure 3.6 Solar panels of this size are often used in small-scale applications where space is limited, such as powering small electronic devices, charging batteries for outdoor equipment, or providing supplemental power in off-grid or remote.

Figure. 3.6 Solar panel

Max. power pm :5.00Wp

Open circuit voltage :21.00v

Max. power current Isc:0.29A

Max. power voltage Vmp:17.00v

Short circuit Isc :0.30A

Max. System Voltage :600v

3.2 Fabrication and Assembly:

Figure: 3.7 Construction and Assembly of the machine.

The main frame of the leaf collecting machine is fabricated, often using welding and cutting techniques to ensure the strength and stability. Components are assembled according to the design specifications.

Operation carried out by using this machine is collecting dry leaves which are present in the garden and to process the leaves into smaller pieces by chopping. The construction and assembly as shown in Fig.3.7.

3.3 CAD 3D Model:

The figure 4.3.1 shows the conceptual design of machine that was prepared by using design software.

Figure: 3.8 3D Model.

Figure. 3.9 shows Solar powered automatic leaf collector 2D drawing.

Figure : 3.9 Drafting of the project model.

4. Results and Discussion

The arrangement of the part includes the Solar panel, Batteries, motor, vacuum blower and the structure of the collector capacity. The collector is arranged in such a way that they are used for collecting the easy disposal of the leaf. The arrangement of the motor is middle of the collector. The body of the motor is visible to the outside of the total body, such that the blade connected with other side of the motor is connected in the collector by making a hole into it.

When the power supply is given through battery initially it is operated in blower mode the leaves that are scattered in the ground are accumulated. Then the accumulated leaf is collected when the blower mode is switched into the vacuum mode, the leaves are sucked by the vacuum blower by the hose connected to it. The sucked leaf is fed into the collector via bend pipe and then directly fed into the blade which is driven by the motor. Then the leaves are chopped into several small pieces by the blade Figure.6.1 and Figure 6.2 shows. The size of the collected leaf is about (5-8) cm when they are collected by the tray, the size of the leaf is found to be (1-2) cm. Thus, the size of the leaf is reduced to small. Then the collected can be used as manure or mulch for the garden purposes. This application of the leaf collector and chopper can be used effectively, and it can be easily operated.

Figure: 6.1 Before processing

Figure : 6.2 After processing

5. Conclusion

With the use of this new technology, we can reduce machine costs significantly and reduce the manual power and can increase the value of garden cleaning. This means cleaning is more frequent, which supports healthy well-being and an increase in overall cleanliness. The machine is a priority over machines that are bulky, heavy and cannot be used for narrow roads. It is much more cost-efficient as compared to other machines in terms of both running cost and production cost. The eco-friendly automatically operated leaf collector machine can work more effectively and efficiently to cost, an area covered, and time required for cleaning garden as compared with the already available machines and it is economical.

The use of innovative technology not only reduces costs significantly but also reduces human effort while increasing the effectiveness of the automatic waste collector. Reduced human effort means more frequent

cleaning which results in an increase in overall cleanliness and supports healthy well-being. Small steps in technological advancement like this will have higher impact in long run in future.

6. References

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